

First record of *Acantharachne seydeli* Giltay, 1935 from South Africa (Arachnida: Araneae)

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ABSTRACT: *Acantharachne* Tullgren, 1910 is a genus known from eight species, all of which are endemic to Africa. One of the species, *A. seydeli* Giltay, 1935, previously known from the Democratic Republic of the Congo, was recorded for the first time from South Africa. The general morphology of live specimens is discussed, with notes on their distribution and conservation status.

Key words: biodiversity, distribution, orb-web, new record, South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA)

INTRODUCTION

The genus *Acantharachne* was erected by Tullgren in 1910 for the species *Acantharachne cornuta* from Tanzania. The genus is represented by eight species and is known only from Africa and Madagascar. From continental Africa the following six species are known: *A. cornuta* Tullgren, 1910 and *A. psyche* Strand, 1913 from Central Africa, *A. regalis* Hirst, 1925 from Cameroon and the Democratic Republic of the Congo (DRC), *A. lesserti* Giltay, 1930 from the DRC, and *A. seydeli* Giltay, 1935 and *A. giltayi* Lessert, 1938 from the DRC and Madagascar (World Spider Catalog, 2022).

The genus has not yet been revised and all the species were described more than 80 years ago. Members of *Acantharachne* received little to no attention since their description, and unfortunately nothing is known about their behaviour. The genus was also not included in the recent phylogenetic study of the orb-weaving spider family Araneidae (Scharff *et al.*, 2020). Levi (2003) suggested that when males of *Acantharachne* are found, it probably will be synonymised with *Cladomelea* Simon, 1895 or *Ordgarius* Keyserling, 1886.

A few specimens were sampled during the South African National Survey of Arachnida and one was identified as *Acantharachne seydeli*. The general morphology of live specimens is discussed, with notes on their distribution and conservation status.

TAXONOMY

Acantharachne seydeli Giltay, 1935

Acantharachne seydeli Giltay, 1935: 10, (f)

Diagnostic characteristics. Female: TL 7–10 mm; carapace dark brown; high, and as wide as long; eyes in two rows; median eyes located on fairly low tubercle; median ocular area wider in front than posteriorly, slightly wider than long; lateral eyes widely spaced from median eyes; there are 8–10 small denticles arranged medially on carapace in a circle (Fig. 2). Clypeus wide, basal part curved forward. Sternum heart shaped; posterior tip inserted between hind legs. Abdomen large relative to carapace (Fig. 3), colour varies from cream (Fig. 2) to fawnish-brown (Fig. 3), mottled white with darker markings; wider than long, furnished dorsally with two circular humps bearing several blunt tubercles; circles well-separated from each other, situated posteriorly on highest part of abdomen; circular areas mottled brown. Legs same colour as carapace; legs variable in some specimens, strongly banded; legs spineless, front legs only slightly longer than hind legs; when resting, front legs arranged in front of body. Male unknown.

Figures 1–3. *Acantharachne seydeli* female: 1–2. Female from Kloof KwaZulu-Natal. 3. Female from Wakefield farm, near Hillcrest. Photo credits: 1–2. Andrea Sander. 3. Peter Webb.

Figures 4–6. *Acantharachne seydeli*: 4. Line drawing from Giltay (1935). 5–6. Female from Mookgopong in ethanol, anterior (5) and dorsal (6) views. Photo credits: Charles Haddad.

Figures 7–9. *Acantharachne seydeli*: 7. Female from Kloof. 8–9. Female from Wakefield. Photo credits: 7. Andrea Sander. 8–9. Peter Webb.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION

Democratic Republic of the Congo, South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA

Limpopo: Rhemardo Holiday Resort, Mookgopong (-24.52, 28.7).

KwaZulu-Natal: Kloof (-29.78, 30.83); Wakefield Farm near Hillcrest (-29.51, 29.90).

BEHAVIOUR

Nothing is known about the behaviour of *Acantharachne*. Emerit (2000) suggested that the Malagasy species may forage using a bolas, although there are no direct observations supporting the implied hunting strategy. They remarkably resemble a bird dropping, thanks to their large, globular abdomen and brownish colour. This is a form of defensive mimicry as the animals that prey on spiders pay little attention to bird droppings, which enables the spiders to rest unnoticed during the day in fairly exposed places. The specimens sampled here rest on the upper surface of leaves. The female from Limpopo was collected while fogging savannah trees.

CONSERVATION STATUS

The species has a wide distribution in the Afrotropical Region but it is under-sampled in South Africa. It can be considered Least Concern.

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